

From Data to Decision: Operationalizing Open Science in Biodiversity Assessments

Dr Aidin Niamir
Senckenberg International Science-Policy Unit

Eroding Trust, Rising Responsibility

- **Technology is Transforming the Information Landscape**
 - Synthetic text, deepfakes, and AI-generated media blur fact and fiction
 - Misinformation undermines public trust in science and institutions
 - Confidence in data authenticity and scientific authority is eroding
- **A Crisis of Credibility**
 - People increasingly struggle to distinguish truth from manipulation
 - Credibility of knowledge and evidence is fragile and declining
 - The consequences are especially critical for biodiversity that requires immediate actions
- **Rising Responsibility of Trusted Institutions**
 - Science-based institutions must act as knowledge brokers; translating complex evidence into actionable insights for policy and the public
 - Thematic and regional such as the Biodiversity Conservation Alliance for Arid Lands (BCAA), are uniquely positioned to lead

The Pyramid of Data to Decision

The Pyramid of Data to Decision

The Pyramid of Data to Decision

What is IPBES?

- **Intergovernmental**
 - **Science-Policy**
 - **Platform**
 - **Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services**
-
- **Independent intergovernmental body**
 - **Established in 2012**
 - **Almost 150 member states**
 - **Provides options for responses and policy-relevant knowledge**
 - **Harness expertise across disciplines**
 - **Diverse knowledge systems**

2016

The assessment report on
**POLLINATORS,
POLLINATION AND
FOOD PRODUCTION**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

The methodological assessment report on
**SCENARIOS AND MODELS
OF BIODIVERSITY AND
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES**

2019

The global
assessment report on
**BIODIVERSITY
AND ECOSYSTEM
SERVICES**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

2024

The thematic assessment report of
**THE UNDERLYING CAUSES OF BIODIVERSITY
LOSS AND THE DETERMINANTS OF
TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE AND OPTIONS
FOR ACHIEVING THE 2050 VISION
FOR BIODIVERSITY**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

The thematic assessment report on
**INTERLINKAGES AMONG
BIODIVERSITY, WATER,
FOOD AND HEALTH**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

2018

The regional assessment report on
**BIODIVERSITY AND
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
FOR AFRICA**

The regional assessment report on
**BIODIVERSITY AND
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
FOR EUROPE AND
CENTRAL ASIA**

The assessment report on
**LAND
DEGRADATION AND
RESTORATION**

The regional assessment report on
**BIODIVERSITY AND
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
FOR THE AMERICAS**

The regional assessment report on
**BIODIVERSITY AND
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
FOR ASIA AND
THE PACIFIC**

2022

The assessment report on
**THE SUSTAINABLE
USE OF WILD SPECIES**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

The assessment report on
**THE DIVERSE VALUES
AND VALUATION OF
NATURE**

SUMMARY FOR POLICYMAKERS

2023

The thematic assessment report on
**INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES
AND THEIR CONTROL**

- Business and Biodiversity (2026)
- Monitoring (2027)
- Spatial Planning and Ecological Connectivity (2028)
- 2nd Global Assessment (2029)

**Body of Data and
Information**

Full report ~ 1500 pages

Summary report ~ 50 pages

Transparency and Trust

The Role of FAIR and CARE Principles in IPBES assessments

- **FAIR is essential for:**
 - Ensuring scientific reproducibility and transparency
 - Enabling open science and evidence-based policymaking
 - Facilitating international collaborations and large-scale modeling
- **CARE is essential for:**
 - Ensuring respect for Indigenous and Local Knowledge
 - Avoiding extractive research practices where local communities lose control over their knowledge
 - Maintaining trust between scientists, local knowledge holders, and policymakers
- **Transparency is the foundation for trust**
 - Transparency ensures the relevance of science even in changing political landscapes
 - Transparency helps to overcome these challenges and strengthen the science-policy engagement

Public Zotero Library

https://www.zotero.org/groups/2352922/ipbes_ias/library

Linked-Open-Data

Body of Knowledge

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10961208>

SENCKENBERG
world of biodiversity

Evaluating the Policy Impact of Biodiversity Data: GBIF-Mediated Research in the IPBES Invasive Alien Species Assessment

Noesgaard D*, Gamba J, Dadvar M, Knug RM, Guddé R, Copas K, Hirsch T, Naimir A
*noesgaard@gbif.org

Introduction

Researchers use GBIF-mediated occurrences to support scientific studies published in peer-reviewed journals at a rate of more than six papers every day. While primary use of GBIF in policy is less apparent, the 2023 Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species (IAS) and their Control¹, published by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) directly used 130 million species occurrences to support its findings. The full impact of open biodiversity data sharing on policy, however, requires examining the extent to which reports and assessments cite the studies that rely on GBIF-mediated data (i.e. secondary use).

Methods

We extracted all references from the 2023 IPBES IAS assessment using the IAS Zotero Public Library². Using unique identifiers (DOIs), we cross-referenced the cited publications with the GBIF Identifier Index³ of papers using GBIF-mediated data. We examined the range of calls to use in matched papers and assessed potential links between specific GBIF data and background and key messages of the assessment report¹, as defined by the IPBES Ontology⁴.

Results

We identified a total of 5,232 references in the IPBES IAS assessment, of which 3,651 publications were unique identifier data by a DOI. When cross-referencing with the GBIF Identifier Index, we identified 130 peer-reviewed studies that relied on GBIF-mediated data to some extent. In 26 of these papers, their authors followed best practices for data citation, and specifically cited the data used via a GBIF DOI.

The 25 papers using DOI-identifiable GBIF-mediated data, cited in the IPBES assessment, used a total of 3.2 billion species occurrences records. Mean use by each paper was 123 million records (min: 625, max: 1.4 billion).

Overall, studies enabled by GBIF data were cited in support of 31 out of 32 of the background messages—covering all 21 key messages—of the assessment.

Conclusion

Biodiversity data shared openly and freely through GBIF directly and indirectly supported the findings of the IPBES IAS assessment through support of 79 per cent of the background messages from which the key messages are derived. These results are facilitated by the free, linked and open structure of IPBES assessments and similar tracking of GBIF-mediated data use.

TRUST

TRANSPARENCY

TRUST

Legitimate Actions

Democratizing Knowledge

Liberating Data

TRANSPARENCY

Accountability

Reliability

Accessibility

Final Reflections:

- **Open Science is a method for building trust, transparency, and relevance in knowledge systems.** A methods of working that embeds transparency, equity, and accountability into how knowledge is generated, shared, and used.
- **Transparency is foundational for trust** in science-policy processes.
- **FAIR and CARE principles** ensure that knowledge is not just technically open, but ethically grounded and socially responsive.
- **Data is only valuable when it's trusted and used.** Traceable knowledge builds the bridge from science to policy.
- **Thematic and regional institutions (e.g. BCAA) are essential knowledge brokers,** not only translating global science into local, actionable insight, but also bringing local realities and knowledge into global assessments and policy agendas.

From Data to Decision: Operationalizing Open Science in Biodiversity Assessments

Dr Aidin Niamir
Senckenberg International Science-Policy Unit